

Wild Food Forests in Tribal Jharkhand: A Community-Led Model for Biodiversity and Resilience

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Traditional agroforestry systems in the tribal uplands of Jharkhand hold vast potential for sustainable food autonomy and biodiversity conservation. This study documents community knowledge and ecological patterns of wild edible and medicinal plants across the Santhal Pargana region. Fieldwork was conducted in Dumka and Godda districts between 2024–2025 through participatory observation, species documentation, and GIS-based mapping. The project aims to revive degraded agroforestry landscapes by integrating native wild species such as *Bauhinia purpurea*, *Diospyros melanoxylon*, and Pteris-type ferns into 'wild food forest' models managed by local communities. Results reveal that these mixed native systems enhance soil fertility, pollinator diversity, and household nutrition security while supporting climate adaptation. The initiative also empowers tribal women and youth through ecological education and participatory conservation. The proposed model demonstrates how traditional ecological knowledge, when merged with modern conservation science, can strengthen rural food systems and ecosystem resilience.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Agroforestry, Tribal Knowledge, Jharkhand, Food Security, Community Resilience